

Potential Biologically Active Agents : IV. Synthesis of N-Substituted Phthalimides

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A series of N-substituted phthalimides have been synthesised. These compounds have been screened for their antibacterial activity.

N-SUBSTITUTED phthalimides have been reported to exhibit antibacterial¹⁻⁴, antifungal³⁻⁵, anthelmintic⁶, antitumour⁷⁻⁹, local anesthetic¹⁰, diuretic¹¹, adrenolytic¹² and schistosomicidal¹³ properties. These observations led the author to synthesise a series of new N-substituted phthalimides for biological screening.

These compounds have been prepared by condensing N-hydroxymethylphthalimide with appropriate aromatic amines in equimolar proportions. In another procedure phthalimide, formaldehyde, and aromatic amines were allowed to react to yield the desired products. N-hydroxymethylphthalimide has also been condensed with 4-nitrophthalimide to furnish compound 7.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are not corrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer in KBr discs.

N-Hydroxymethylphthalimide :

Phthalimide (10.20 g) was suspended in 100 ml of distilled water. To this suspension there was added 5.20 ml of 37% formalin. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hr and was allowed to remain at room temperature overnight. The white crystalline solid thus obtained was filtered and dried in air; m.p. 138°-140°, lit.¹⁵ m.p. 138°-141°; yield 10.0 g.

N-Substituted Phthalimides :

Method I : N-Hydroxymethylphthalimide (1.77 g; 0.01 mole) was dissolved in 15 ml of hot ethanol. To this solution amino compound (0.01 mole) was added with shaking. The reaction mixture was then heated on a steam bath for 2 hr. The contents of the flask were allowed to cool. The solid products thus separated were recrystallised.

Method II : To a suspension of 4-nitrophthalimide (1.92 g; 0.01 mole) in 25 ml of hot ethanol there was added 2 ml of 37% formalin and amino compound

TABLE 1—N-SUBSTITUTED PHTHALIMIDES

No.	R ₁ or name of the compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analyses %	
					Found	Calcd.
R = H						
1.	4-COOH	228 ^d	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄	—	—
2.	4-COOCH ₃	181—182	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	N, 8.70	9.02
3.	3-COOCH ₃	168—170	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	C, 66.25 H, 5.00 N, 8.82	65.79 4.54 9.02
4. ^a	3-COOC ₂ H ₅	150—152	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	N, 8.48	8.64
5.	2-COOCH ₃	215—216	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	N, 9.53	9.02
6.	2-COOC ₂ H ₅	225—227	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	N, 8.74	8.64
7.	N-(4-Nitrophthalimidomethyl)-phthalimide	168—169	50	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₃ O ₆	N, 12.65	11.97
8.	N-(N-Phthalimidomethyl)-4(4-chlorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole	210 d	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	N, 11.43	11.36

Table 1 *Contd.*

R = NO ₂						
9.	4-COOH	220 d	45	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	C, 56.30 H, 3.76 N, 12.25	56.30 3.25 12.31
10 ^a .	4-COOCH ₃	213	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆	C, 57.70 H, 3.62 N, 11.66	57.45 3.68 11.82
11 ^c .	4-COOC ₂ H ₅	188—190	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₆	C, 58.80 H, 4.55 N, 11.15	58.53 4.09 11.38
12.	3-COOH	209—210	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	C, 55.75 H, 3.56 N, 11.84	56.30 3.25 12.31
13 ^d .	3-COOCH ₃	161—162	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆	N, 11.62	11.82
14.	3-COOC ₂ H ₅	165—166	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₆	N, 11.55	11.38
15.	2-COOH	184—186	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	N, 11.93	12.31
16.	2-COOCH ₃	193—194	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆	C, 57.20 H, 3.43 N, 11.41	57.45 3.68 11.82
17.	2-COOC ₂ H ₅	184—185	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₆	C, 58.80 H, 4.38 N, 11.53	58.53 4.09 11.38
18.	4-Phenyl	188—190	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄	C, 67.00 H, 4.43 N, 11.56	67.56 4.05 11.26
19.	2-Phenyl	174—175	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄	C, 67.35 H, 4.35 N, 11.08	67.56 4.05 11.26

No. 1-8 were prepared by method I and were recrystallised from ethanol.

No. 9-19 were prepared by method II and were recrystallised from acetone.

IR(cm⁻¹): a, 3333(NH), 1709(C=O); b, 3367(NH), 1724(C=O); c, 3333(NH), 1724(C=O); d, 3333(NH), 1718(C=O). e, Lit. (15) m.p. 232 d.

(0.01 mole) dissolved in boiling ethanol (20 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min. At the end of this period the contents of the flask were cooled. The solid mass thus separated was filtered and recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

The analyses, m.ps. and other pertinent data are given in Table 1.

Biological Data :

The compounds reported in Table 1 were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against three organisms: *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Aerobacter aerogenes* by agar diffusion technique¹⁴.

The agar medium was inoculated with 1 ml of 24 hr. old cultures of the test organism. Filter paper discs (5 mm diameter) saturated with the solution of the test compound (10 mg/ml in acetone) were placed on the agar after drying up the solvent. After an incubation period of 24 hr. the zones of inhibition around the discs were measured. Biological data for the active compounds are provided in Table 2. Bacterial cultures maintained at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow were used in this study.

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL DATA OF N-SUBSTITUTED PHTHALIMIDES

Compound	Microbial Spectrum		
	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Staph. aureus</i>	<i>Aerobacter aerogenes</i>
6.	+	+	+
7.	+	+	+
9.	+	+	+
12.	+	+	+
13.	—	+	—

A negative sign indicates no activity.

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